

Online Job Search Engine

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Abstract—

The project entitled "Online Job Searching" deals with registration of job. Here the job seekers should register their details before beginning the search. This is dealt with a minimal set of sample data and procedures that have been carried out online. The developed software acts as a prototype for job procedures. Through this project, we can also check for the availability of job in particular place as well as company the name will also get mentioned. The timings and other information can also be viewed online. This also displays options for job category. The user can select and register a specific category in which they are familiar with according to the job type its detail will be shown. The project also attempts to computerized activities. An attempt is made to introduce new concepts in the developed project. This project has been developed in such a way to replace the human resources with more efficient computer resource. It also enables the user to view the activities of the job and enable the user for online registration.

KEYWORDS : "ONLINE," 2018

Generic Technology Keywords: Database, User Interface Specific Technology
Keywords: Apache Server, MySQL Project
Keywords: Business Object, Data Access Layer
SDLC Keywords: Analysis, Design, Implementation, Testing

INTRODUCTION

This web based jobs searching engine basically concerned with different job services provided by different companies. It is also concerned with details of jobseekers. Jobseeker can view the list of different jobs and can apply for jobs. Then the company going to select the required job seekers for their qualification and update the database. The portal going to follow different companies' policy. Their be an admin to manage all things.

Title Of Project: "Online Job Search Engine" Front End Used: Php

Back End Used: Mysql

PURPOSE

The purpose of the designing the online job portal it is to give the job seekers a platform for finding a right and a satisfactory job according to their qualification it also connect the job seekers with the major Agencies.

it is also provide the job portal for job seekers to submit their CV and apply for job postings and employers can select the best employees for available CV based on their payment option selection this is the basically a job portal where the job seeker Apply for job and employer was the job and selects prospective application.

the job portal is a prepared for provide all categories of the job and head to the get various type of job the main purpose of the job portal it is to provide the facility to the job seekers for getting the quick job so its unable application to the search for the job in a convent and manner and to enable employees to the find suitable candidate.

OBJECTIVE

This project is aimed at developing an

online search Portal for the Placement Details for job seekers. The system is an online application that can be accessed throughout the organization and outside as well with proper login provided. This system can be used as an Online Job Portal for job seekers. Job Seekers logging should be able to upload their information in the form of a CV. Visitors/ Company representatives logging in may also access/search any information put up by Job aspirants.

Functional components of the project:

1. A person should be able to

- Access/ Search CVs/information from the first page (only read access).
- Login to the system through the first page of the application.
- Change the password after logging into the system
- Upload his/her CV.
- See/change his/her details.
- Get help about the application on how to use the different features of the system.

2. An admin login should be present who can read as well as remove any uploads. (The & Of, 2011)

SCOPE

The scope of the online job portal includes: The Online job Portal System that is to be developed provides the members with jobs information, online applying for jobs and many other facilities. The basic scope of the project is given as under.

- Job Seekers
- Area Recruiters Area
- Administrator's Panel(The & Of, 2011)

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

ABOUT PHP:-

METHODOLOGY

This Project Provide a common platform for job seekers and Recruiters. The Job Seekers can able to register for this site & get the opportunity for job according to his/her qualification. They also get the information

about the well-known Hotels, Restaurants and Shopping malls etc.

The Online Job searching engine Project will be having another major part that is administration part. The Admin user can able to login into the application for managing the information if any modified is required.

The Online Job searching engine System is a package to be used by agencies to improve the efficiency of business. The Online Job searching engine System to be developed benefits greatly the members. The system provides jobs catalogue and information to members and helps them decide on the jobs to apply. The Admin can keep the jobs catalogue updated all the time so that the members (Job seekers and the agencies) get the updated information all the time. The main users are users: Admin, Members who are the Job seekers and the agencies.

After long discussion with our mentor team, we have taken a decision to implement requirements in this project which are documented in "Functional Requirement" section.

FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

ADMIN MODULE

➤ Admin can Manage a Package or plan for Jobseeker.

➤ Admin can View Register member and Manage Register Member in our site.

➤ Admin Can View Jobseeker Details.

➤ Admin Manage Company Details.

➤ Admin can View Job alert.

➤ Admin can View Apply job.

➤ Admin can Manage Compose message Details.

➤ Admin can View Inbox .

➤ Admin can View post comment.

➤ Admin can View Feedback.(To, n.d.)

COMPANY MODULE

➤ Company can Login in our site.

➤ Company can Update company profile.

➤ Company can Create job criteria.

➤ Company can view Compose message by Jobseeker and Admin.

➤ Company can View inbox. 3/13/2015(To, n.d.)

JOBSEEKER MODULE

➤ Jobseeker can Login in our site.

➤ Jobseeker can View different different job plan.

➤ Jobseeker can easily view company information.

➤ Jobseeker can Update his/her profile information.

➤ Jobseeker can Job alert.

➤ Jobseeker can Apply for suitable job plan.

➤ Jobseeker can easily Cancel member registration.

➤ Jobseeker can View his/her Inbox. ?Jobseeker can easily Post comment on our site.(To, n.d.)

PHP, which stands for "PHP: Hypertext Pre-processor", is an HTML-embedded scripting language. Much of its syntax is borrowed from C, Java and Perl with a couple of unique PHP-specific features thrown in. The goal of the language is to allow web developers to write dynamically generated pages quickly.

Example:-An introductory example,

```
<html><head>
```

```
<title>Example</title></head>
```

```
<body><?php echo "Hi, I'm a PHP script!"; ?>
```

```
</body>
```

```
</html>
```

Notice how this is different from a CGI script written in other languages like Perl or C – instead of writing a program with lots of commands to output HTML, you write an HTML script with a some embedded code to do something (in this case, output some text). The PHP code is enclosed in special start and end tags that allow you to jump into and out of PHP mode.

ABOUT MySQL:-

MySQL is a high performance, relational database server based on MYSQL. It is built on CLIENT/SERVER architecture, which means a frontend or client component, and a back end, or server component. MySQL server forms the back-end component in this architecture and is responsible for providing all the standard DBMS functions. The client component, for which there are many different possibilities, is responsible for providing all of the user interface and application-processing function. The language used to communicate between clients and database.

For scripting, providing style and for designing purpose JavaScript, CSS and html are used.

JavaScript :-

Java script is embedded into HTML documents and is executed with in them. Java script is browser dependent. JavaScript is an interpreted language that can be interpreted by the browser at run time. Java script is loosely typed language. Java script is an object-based language. Java script is an Event- Driven language and supports event handlers to specify the functionality of a button.

HTML :-

The HTML code is made up of characters that live inside angled brackets — these are called HTML elements. Elements are usually made up of two tags: an opening tag and a closing tag. (The closing tag has an extra forward slash in it.) Each HTML element tells the browser something about the information that sits between its opening and closing tags.

CSS:-

CSS stands for cascading style sheet. CSS is used for formatting to webpages. CSS is used using {property: value} curly braces. CSS can be provided internally or externally. There are three types of selector, CSS can be used either in tag, ID or class selector.

Example:-body {color: red}

PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

This project is aimed for promoting the Online Job. This project is developed mainly for easily aces to SEARCHING JOB. The purpose of the project entitled as job searching is to provide user friendly environment for Seekers to register and search their online job which is simple, fast and cost effective. Traditionally, it was done manually. The main function of the system is to register and manage online data.

PROBLEM FORMULATION :-

Online job engine data base have to collect the information of various companies who want to recruit seekers and notify person time to time about them. It is a time consuming activity of managing, updating and informing specific student.

1. Sometime many companies recruit the seekers CV, so it is difficult to Recruiters for inform the passed out seekers.

2. Recruiters and seekers cannot interact easily with each other.

PROBLEM SOLUTION :-

1. Now all the information can be filled through software which reduces paper work and also there is a maintained database which is useful for Recruiters as well as seekers.

2. Recruiters and seekers can interact easily with each other.

3. With the help of the software seekers can easily interact with Recruiters also.

SYSTEM SPECIFICATION**Hardware:-**

IBM compatible , Intel Pentium 4, Intel core-i3 based PC with a monitor , keyboard and mouse, system must have 1 GB Ram, Hard disk 80 GB or of available memory. Operating

System:-

➤ Windows XP or Windows 7 or Windows 8. S/W needed:-

➤ Platform specification: Apache Server
➤ User Interface Design: HTML, CSS and JavaScript

➤ Front end: PHP

- Back end: MySQL
- Software: WAMP Server

Standarbrowser :-

Google chrome, Firefox , Internet Explorer 6.0 or Any patible Browser Com(To, n.d.)

NEED -

1. Efficiently maintains the details about the Seekers & Recruiters.
2. Simultaneously updates changes made to any data, item in the entire database.
3. It is faster than manual system.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

This document depicts the low level design document of the Online Job searching engine project. This document includes the identified classes and relationship between the classes, functional architecture and sequence diagram of the major functional requirements.

The intended audiences of this document are –

- Team member of the Job searching engine project
- Mentor of the Job searching engine project

DATA FLOW AND ER-DIAGRAM

This document is created for documenting all major classes which are used in project. The relationship between the classes and how the classes are interacting (Process flow / DFD diagram) are documented in low level design document.

Data Flow Diagram- A graphical tool used to describe and analyse the moment of data through a system manual or automated including the process, stores of data, and delays in the system. DFD is the basis from which other components are developed. The transformation of data from input to output, through processes, may be described logically and independently of the physical components associated with the system. The two types of Data flow diagrams are:

- Physical DFD
- Logical DFD

Entity Relationship (E-R) Diagram:-

A graphical representation of the entities and the relationships between them. Entity relationship diagrams are a useful medium to achieve a common understanding of data among users and application developers. (The & Of, 2011)

ADMIN ACTIVITY INPUT/OUTPUT SCREEN HOME PAGE

Activity Diagram

JOB PROVIDER ACTIVITY

(“ONLINE,” 2018)DATA STRUCTURE

Database name: job

1. Table name: user_master

Description: To store the admin username and password.

Primary Key: id

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
1	Userid	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT
2	UserName	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
3	Password	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	

2. Table name: employer_reg Description: To store the bookings. Primary Key: empld

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes	Null	Default	Extra
1	Employerid	int(11)			No	None	AUTO_INCREMENT
2	CompanyName	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
3	ContactPerson	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
4	Address	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
5	City	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
6	Email	varchar(40)	latin1_swedish_ci		No	None	
7	Mobile	bigint(20)			No	None	

3. Table name: jobseeker_reg Description: To store the issues of seeker. Primary Key: id

#	Name	Type	Collation	Attributes
1	JobSeekId	int(11)		
2	JobSeekerName	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci	
3	Address	varchar(100)	latin1_swedish_ci	
4	City	varchar(20)	latin1_swedish_ci	
5	Email	varchar(40)	latin1_swedish_ci	

Page name: admin page

Page name: employer page

Page name: Jobseeker page

BENEFITS

The project is identified by the merits of the system offered to the user. The merits of this project are as follows: -

- It's a web-enabled project.
- This project offers user to enter the data through simple and interactive forms. This is very helpful for the client to enter the desired information through so much simplicity.

- The user is mainly more concerned about the validity of the data, whatever he is entering. There are checks on every stages of any new creation, data entry or updation so that the user cannot enter the invalid data, which can create problems at later date.

- Sometimes the user finds in the later stages of using project that he needs to update some of the information that he entered earlier. There are options for him by which he can update the records. Moreover there is restriction for his that he cannot change the primary data field. This keeps the validity of the data to longer extent.

- User is provided the option of monitoring the records he entered earlier. He can see the desired records with the variety of options provided by him.

- From every part of the project the user is provided with the links through framing so that he can go from one option of the project to other as per the requirement. This is bound to be simple and very friendly as per the user is concerned. That is, we can sat that the project is user

Books

REFERENCES

friendly which is one of the primary concerns of any good project.

- Decision making process would be greatly enhanced because of faster processing of information since data collection from information available on computer takes much less time then manual system.

- Allocating of sample results becomes much faster because at a time the user can see the records of last years.

- Easier and faster data transfer through latest technology associated with the computer and communication.

- Through these features it will increase the efficiency, accuracy and transparency,.(To, n.d.)

LIMITATIONS

- The size of the database increases day-by-day, increasing the load on the database back up and data maintenance activity.

- Training for simple computer operations is necessary for the users working on the system.

- Usability

THREATS TO SYSTEM SECURITY

A procedure for protecting systems makes sure that the facility is physically secure, provides a recovery/restart capability, and has access to backup files. If we list in order of probability the threats to system security or data integrity, research shows that the most damage comes from errors and omissions-people making mistakes. The threat of external attack on a computer system is virtually last. This means that in establishing a priority sequence, one would probably want to start from within the firm and workout. The list of potential threats is:

- I. Errors and omissions.
 - II. Disgruntled and dishonest employees.
 - III. Fire
 - IV. Natural Disasters
 - V. External attack
- ("dipti shoping papaer," n.d.)

CONCLUSIONS

Here, I have designed a project "Online Job search engine". All the application codes are in PHP with the AJAX and JQUERY backend. This portal provides all the features with the support of extension JS-JOB Plug-in. The plugin, I am using is free trial, so its functionalities are limited. My project satisfies all the functional requirements mentioned in the project, however, it doesn't contain any module. In future I will add this feature in this project with some other variation, I would like to design more user friendly search engine system.

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